

NOTES

Terpenoids and Related Compounds: Part X¹. Chemical Investigation of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* Poit

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Pedilanthus tithymaloides^{2,3}, an ornamental species (Fam. Euphorbiaceae) is a West Indian succulent shrub with a scarlet slipper shaped involucre, which is much cultivated in native gardens and planted in hedges. Since no chemical investigation of the plant have been reported in literature, we have undertaken the chemical examination of the plant. In the present communication we record the isolation and characterisation of the neutral constituents, viz., epi-friedelanol acetate, friedlin, epi-friedelanol, 1-dotriacotanol and β -sitosterol from the whole plant materials.

The benzene extract of the dried and powdered plant material of *P. tithymaloides* was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The petroleum eluate* after rechromatography and upon concentration gave a solid (A) on long standing. This solid after crystallisation from chloroform-methanol melted with a range of 225—35°, $\nu_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 1735 and 1235 (acetate), 1705 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), which on chromatoplate showed two distinct spots (R_f 0.6 and 0.35, using silica gel G as adsorbent and benzene : petroleum (1:1) as developer). Further elution with petroleum gave a second solid m.p. 259-60°, $[\alpha]_D - 36^{45}$ (single spot on chromatoplate), which showed positive test with Libermann-Burchardt reagent and negative test with tetranitromethane and was found to be identical with an authentic specimen of friedelin (m.m.p. and I.R.). Alkaline hydrolysis of the above mixture (A) and subsequent chromatography of the reaction product afforded two different solids m.p. 255-58° and 277-79°, coming out in different fractions of eluating solvents each showing homogeneous on a chromatoplate. The first solid m.p. 255-58° after crystallisation from chloroform-methanol gave crystals m.p. 259-61°, $[\alpha]_D - 34^\circ$, has been found to be identical with an authentic specimen of friedelin (m.m.p, I. R. and R_f values). The second solid m.p. 277-9° after crystallisation from chloroform-methanol gave crystals m.p. 279-81°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$, gave Libermann-Burchardt reaction for triterpene (Found : C, 84.32; H, 12.18; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{52}O$: C, 84.10; H, 12.00), acetate m.p. 292-3°, $[\alpha]_D + 40^\circ$. This solid

1. "Terpenoids and related compounds", Part IX, H. N. Khastgir and B. P. Pradhan, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1969, **46**, 331.
2. J. D. Hooker, "The Flora of British India" Vol. V, L. Reeve and Co. Ltd., Reprinted 1954, page 239.
3. H. Santapau, "The Flora of Purandhar". Oxford book and Stationary Co., page 119.
- * Petroleum used throughout the investigation had b.p. 60-80°.
4. All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Rotations were taken in chloroform solution unless otherwise stated.
5. Drake and Jacobsen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1570, 1954.

has been identified as suggested by their m.p. and specific rotation values^{6,7}, as epi-friedelanol, by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p and I.R.). This fact establishes that epi-friedelanol is present in the mixture as its acetate.

The solid obtained from petroleum : benzene (4:1) eluate after crystallisation from chloroform-methanol gave crystals m.p. 279-81°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$, (Found : C, 84.44; H, 11.96; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{52}O$: C, 84.10; H, 12.00), acetate m.p. 290-92°, $[\alpha]_D + 40^\circ$, (Lit⁸. m.p. 290-94°, $[\alpha]_D + 45^\circ$) and was identified as epi-friedelanol (m.m.p. and I.R. comparison of its acetate with authentic specimen).

The petroleum : benzene (3:2) eluate afforded a solid which on crystallisation from benzene gave solid m.p. 89-90°. It developed no coloration with tetranitromethane. Its analysis corresponds with the molecular formula $C_{32}H_{66}O$, (Found : C, 82.93; H, 14.74; Calc. for $C_{32}H_{66}O$: C, 82.42, H, 14.16%), molecular wt. 472 (Rast) and it showed a peak in its I.R. spectrum at 3500 cm^{-1} characteristic of hydroxyl group. Presence of this group was supported by the preparation of its acetate m.p. 74-6°. These data agreed fairly well with those reported⁹ for 1-dotriacontanol, $CH_3(CH_2)_{30}CH_2OH$. The compound showed no depression in the m.p. with an authentic sample of 1-dotriacontanol. Further elution with the same solvent mixture afforded another solid m.p. 134-5°, $[\alpha]_D - 40^\circ$, acetate m.p. 126-7°, $[\alpha]_D - 38^\circ$, (Found : C, 81.66; H, 11.34; Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81 : 54; H, 11.48%) (Lit¹⁰ m.p. 126-7°, $[\alpha]_D - 42^\circ$) and has been identified as β -sitosterol (m.m.p. and I.R. comparison of β -sitosterol and its acetate with an authentic sample respectively).

The acidic fraction upon usual processing did not furnish any crystalline solid.

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6. Susumu Nomomura, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan.*, 1955, **75**, 80.
7. T. Takemotu and Nodoka Yahagi, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan.*, 1955, **75**, 1164.
8. Jefferies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 473.
9. I. Heilborn and H. Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. 3, Erye and Spottiswoode Publishers Ltd., Reprinted 1965, page 1322.
10. Reference 9, Vol. 5, page 2402.